

STUDENTS' MATHEMATICS PERFORMANCE AND PROBLEM-SOLVING SKILLS IN CONTEXTUALIZED CULTURE-BASED INSTRUCTION (Province of Guimaras Culture)

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the students' Mathematics performance and problem-solving skills in contextualized culture-based instruction. It also sought to find out if there was a significant difference in the students' Mathematics performance and problem-solving skills before and after exposure to contextualized culture-based instruction, and if there was a significant relationship between students' Mathematics performance and problem-solving skills in contextualized culture-based instruction. The researcher purposely chose the Grade 9 students at Supang National High School of the school year 2019-2020 as respondents. The Mathematics Performance Test comprised a 30-item multiple-choice type of test with a reliability coefficient of KR20 value of 0.729 and 0.804 of the Problem-Solving Test which comprised 5-item open-ended word problems. The study utilized the mean, standard deviation, and paired-sample t-test set at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The study revealed that students' exposure to contextualized culture-based instruction upgraded students' Mathematics performance from "satisfactory" to "very satisfactory" and their problem-solving skills from "did not meet expectation" to "outstanding". Consequently, students performed better in Mathematics and greatly developed their problem-solving skills after they were exposed to contextualized culture-based instruction which simply meant that this teaching strategy is effective. Moreover, there was a significant relationship between students' Mathematics performance and problem-solving skills when exposed to contextualized culture-based instruction. This explains that students' Mathematics performance can be explained or predicted by their problem-solving skills. Students who performed well in Mathematics are also expected to perform well in problem-solving.

Keywords: *Mathematics Performance, Problem Solving Skills, Contextualized, Cultured-Based*

INTRODUCTION

The 1987 Philippine Constitution in Article XIV, Section 14 states that, “The State shall foster the preservation, enrichment, and dynamic evolution of a Filipino national culture based on the principle of unity in diversity in a climate of free artistic and intellectual expression”.

Furthermore, it is also stated in Article XIV, Section 5. (1), expresses that, “The State shall take into account regional and sectoral needs and conditions and shall encourage local planning in the development of educational policies and programs”.

A contextualized instruction is an effective teaching strategy where students can construct new knowledge by connecting their educational content or their daily lessons to their previous knowledge, everyday contexts and students’ own experiences, intuitive knowledge, values, culture, and traditions of the local community. Lomibao (2014) postulated that contextualized problems are effective in improving and enhancing students’ problem-solving achievement and conceptual understanding in terms of interpreting, applying, and explaining algebra concepts.

According to the National Council for Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM, 2000), the mastery of the mathematical concepts and problem-solving skills are two very important skills to acquire in modern mathematics which is different from those days. Yet, many students were reported facing difficulties in mathematics particularly in mathematics problem solving. “Mathematics problems are really difficult”, “I did not know how to do it, that is why I did not finish it”, “I don’t like Math”. These statements were quite familiarly heard from students. They seemed to be struggling especially with mathematics problem-solving. Given a 5-item open ended word problem during periodical test, only 10 out of 40 students took time to read and tried answering the problem and only 5 out of 10 who tried could get the correct answer.

In most cases, mathematics teachers introduced mathematics concepts where situations were usually taken from foreign books and used situations which were not familiar to the students. Thus, this led to difficulties of students in linking their experiences at home and community to their Mathematics lessons. This cultural disconnection poses additional obstacles for students to learn basic skills in mathematics. Perin (2011), in a study on facilitating student learning through contextualization, also found out that practitioners who use contextualization observe positive results and the available quantitative evidence indicates that it has the potential to increase students’ achievement.

Children need to learn how mathematics applies to everyday life and how mathematics relates to other curriculum areas as well. Hence, teachers need to relate daily lessons to students’ interests and experience. Instruction should incorporate real world contexts and children’s experiences and, when possible, should use children’s language, viewpoints, and culture.

If the teaching and learning process is not equally effective for all students, the difficulties in acquiring mathematical skills by the students could get worsen. Thus, Mathematics should be taught in schools using situations that represent a particular culture of the students. In this study, the researcher will introduce Mathematics lessons integrating Guimaras culture for the students to learn not only concepts of mathematics, but also, let students feel that the lessons are interesting and engaging.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the students' mathematics performance and problem-solving skills when exposed to contextualized culture-based instruction. Specifically, it sought to answer the following problems:

1. What is the students' Mathematics performance and problem-solving skills before and after their exposure to contextualized culture-based instruction?
2. Is there a significant difference in students' Mathematics performance and problem-solving skills before and after their exposure to contextualized culture-based instruction?
3. Is there a significant relationship between students' Mathematics performance and problem skills after their exposure to contextualized culture-based instruction?

METHODOLOGY

The Respondents. The researcher opted to conduct this study in her class purposely to have a full control of the respondents and to avoid disturbance on the schedule of classes of the other teachers during the conduct of the study.

The respondents of this study were the 42 Grade 9 students who belong in one (1) section presently enrolled at Supang National High School in school year 2019-2020.

The Data Gathering Methods. The researcher secured permit to conduct this study from the office of the school principal of Supang National High School. Since the respondents were minors, the researcher needs to inform the respondents' parents by sending them the parent-consent letter.

This study will made use of the researcher-made contextualized culture-based teaching and learning lesson exemplars drafted in 4As (Activity, Analysis, Abstraction, Application) format that cover Quadratic Equation, Rational Algebraic Expressions, and Inequalities. These topics were discussed in six (6) weeks on the first quarter of the school year as indicated in the Grade 9 Mathematics learning competencies in the K to

12 Curriculum Guide. See the sample of the contextualized culture-based teaching and learning lesson exemplars on pages as follows.

Content Standard:

The learner demonstrates understanding of key concepts of quadratic equations.

Performance Standard:

The learner is able to investigate thoroughly mathematical relationship in various situations.

Lesson 1: Illustrations of Quadratic Equations

Learning Competency: M9AL-1a-1: Illustrate quadratic equation.

Resources/References:

- 1) Mathematics Grade 9 Learners Module pp.11-17, and
- 2) The Division Curriculum Matrix for Curriculum Localization, Division of Guimaras, September 12, 2013 by Arthur J. Cotimo, Ed.D
- 3) Photos: <https://www.boracay-activities.ph/activities/sailing.html>
<http://www.thenewstoday.info/2008/09/29/20080929pic.html>

Learners' Materials: Pencil, Ruler, Work Sheet and Activity Notebook.

Procedure:

Activity: (Time allotted: 10 minutes)

The teacher will gather first students' ideas about "Palayag Festival" by asking the following questions:

1. Who among you have already joined the "Palayag Festival"?
2. What are your experiences or observations during the festival?

The teacher explains that the Palayag Festival is a cultural festival that maximizes the rich traditions of the oldest municipality of Guimaras, the Buenavista. It is celebrated every 3rd Sunday of January. The Palayag is defined as to sail through "Layag" using water vessel. This is the "Kinaradto" or the oldest form of sea travel between Buenavista wharf and Iloilo.

The teacher will show a picture of a sail boat or banca (de Layag) to the learner and illustrate on how to solve the area of the "Layag" in the picture given the following dimensions.

- a) Base = 6 inches
- b) Height = 8 inches

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 A = \frac{1}{2}bh & \text{or } A = \frac{bh}{2} \\
 = \frac{1}{2}(6 \text{ inches})(8 \text{ inches}) & \text{or } A = \frac{(6 \text{ inches})(8 \text{ inches})}{2} \\
 = \frac{1}{2}(48 \text{ square inches}) & \text{or } A = \frac{48 \text{ square inches}}{2} \\
 A = 24 \text{ square inches} & \text{or } A = 24 \text{ square inches}
 \end{array}$$

The teacher will ask the following questions:

1. How many dimensions are required in solving the area of the layag? What are those dimensions?
2. What happen to the unit of measure in solving an area?

Analysis: (Time allotted: 5 minutes)

The teacher will ask the following questions to the leaners:

1. Supposed the base of your "Layag" is unknown and its height is three feet longer than its base and has an area of ten square feet. What equation would represent the given situation?
2. How will you simplify the equation to find the height and the base of the layag? Show your process on the board.

Abstraction: (Time allotted: 15 minutes)

The teacher will explain that the previous activity describes a Quadratic Equation in one variable. It is a mathematical sentence of degree 2. The standard form of the Quadratic Equation is $ax^2 + bx + c = 0$, where a, b, and c are real numbers, ax^2 is the quadratic term, bx is the linear term, and c is the constant term. The a in the quadratic term should not be equal to zero.

The teacher will ask the leaner, why a in the quadratic term of the Quadratic Equation should not be equal to zero?

The teacher will show examples of a quadratic equation in standard form and a quadratic equation which is not in a standard form.

Example 1:

The $3x^2 - 2x + 4 = 0$ is a quadratic equation in standard form with $a = 3$, $b = -2$, and $c = 4$.

Example 2:

The $3x(x - 2) = 10$ is a quadratic equation. However, it is not written in standard form.

$$\begin{array}{l}
 3x(x - 2) = 10 \\
 3x^2 - 6x - 10 = 10 - 10 \\
 3x^2 - 6x - 10 = 0 \quad \text{where, } a = 3, b = -6, \text{ and } c = -10.
 \end{array}$$

Generalization: (Time allotted: 5 minutes)

The teacher will ask the following questions to generalize the lesson:

- 1) How will you know if a certain Guimaras culture illustrates Quadratic Equation?
- 2) What other Guimaras culture will this quadratic equation be observed?

Application: (Time allotted: 15 minutes)

The teacher will direct the learners to answer the following questions based on the given situation below:

Negros had no good harbor for bigger ship way back 1970's, therefore they built the Sugar Bulk at the Jordan Wharf and used Guimaras as transship point to Iloilo.

The length of the floor area of the Sugar Bulk warehouse is 10 meters longer than its width and has an area of 500 square meters.

Remnant of the flourishing sugar industry in Iloilo during the 70s, the Guimaras Bulk Sugar Installation in Jordan, Guimaras.

- 1) Write an equation that would represent the floor area of the Sugar Bulk warehouse, then tell whether if it is a quadratic equation or not? Explain your answer.
- 2) How will you transform the equation of the floor area of the Sugar Bulk warehouse to the standard form of the quadratic equation?
- 3) How will you determine the value of a, b, and c in the quadratic equation of the floor area Sugar Bulk warehouse?

Evaluation: (Time allotted: 10 minutes)

The teacher will direct the learners to think of at least one culture-based real-life situations and illustrate it in quadratic equation, formulate and write the equation into standard form and identify the value of a, b, and c.

Assignment:

The teacher will give the following items as an assignment to be checked next meeting.

The teacher will instruct the learners to illustrate the given Guimaras culture into quadratic equation and determine the value of a , b and c .

1. The Guimaras island is one of the famous islands in the Philippines that is known for its sweetest mango. The Guimaras mango has many products like jam, dried mangoes, and the mango pizza. Supposed the rectangular-shaped mango pizza has an area of 384 square inches and its length is 8 inches longer than its width.
2. Most of the products in the Buenavista Pasalubong Center which is located near Buenavista Wharf are mango flavored since Guimaras is known for its sweetest mango. One of the products is the mango flavored Otap. The rectangular box that contained the mango flavored Otap has an area of 10 square centimeters, and its length is three centimeters greater than its width.
3. The name of barangay Avila came from the native dialect “Abi, La” (hey grandma) or “may I see Grandma” which was later spelled Avila. The barangay celebrates the “Tabagakan Festival” every year since making of dry tabagak is one of the livelihoods of the natives. Mary and James joined the “Tabagakan Festival” before going home they bought tabagak for their pasalubong. James bought a total of 40 kilos of “tabagak” or dry fish, where James bought three kilos more than Mary.

Administration of Pre-test was done before the conduct of the study. The test instrument comprises of two parts. Part I, The Mathematics Performance Test (MPT), includes the 30-item multiple choice type of test to assess students’ mathematics performance. One point was given for every correct answer.

Part I. Students’ Mean Scores in Mathematics Performance Test were categorized based on the following levels:

Mean Scale	Descriptive Rating	Description
24.01 - 30.00	Outstanding	Students are in advanced level of performance in the expected learning competencies or correctly answered 93% to 100% of the test which marked excellence.
18.01 – 24.00	Very Satisfactory	Students are in proficient level of performance in the expected learning competencies or answered 63% to 92% of the test correctly.
12.01 - 18.00	Satisfactory	Students performed close to proficiency in the expected learning competencies or answered 43% to 62% of the test correctly.

6.01 - 12.00	Fairly Satisfactory	Students are in developing level of performance in the expected learning competencies or answered 23% to 42% of the test correctly.
0.00 – 6.00	Did not meet expectations	Students poorly performed in the expected learning competencies or answered 0% to the 23% of the test correctly.

Part II, Problem Solving Test (PST), composed of five-item open-ended mathematical word problems involving quadratic equations that sought to measure the participants' problem-solving skills. Ten points were given to every complete and correct answer in the PST.

Students' Mean Scores in Problem Solving Test categorized as to the following levels:

Mean Scale	Descriptive Rating	Description
40.01 - 50.00	Outstanding	Students are in advanced problem-solving skills in the expected learning competencies or correctly answered 85% to 100% of the test which marked excellence.
30.01 - 40.00	Very Satisfactory	Students are in proficient level of problem-solving skills in the expected learning competencies or answered 65% and below 85% of the test correctly.
20.01 - 30.00	Satisfactory	Students have a close to proficiency problem solving skills in the expected learning competencies or answered 45% to 65% of the test correctly.
10.01 - 20.00	Fairly Satisfactory	Students are in developing level of problem-solving skills in the expected learning competencies or answered 25% to 45% of the test correctly.
0.00 – 10.00	Did not meet expectations	Students have a poor problem-solving skill in the expected learning competencies or answered 0% to 25% of the test correctly.

The instrument was pilot tested to other students who are not respondents of the said study to determine its reliability. The reliability coefficient of the MPT was KR 20 value of 0.729 and of the PST was 0.804 which were above 0.75 denoting that the test had high internal consistency. The result of the examination of each group was analyzed to draw conclusion about the effect of the contextualized culture-based teaching and learning lesson exemplars on the students' mathematics performance and problem-solving skills.

The Data Analysis Plan. The contextualized culture-based teaching and learning lesson exemplars were implemented in six weeks on the mathematics class of the respondents. Conduct of Post-test was done, and students were given an hour to finish

the MPT and another hour on the next day to answer the PST. The researcher retrieved, checked, collated, sorted, and classified the accomplished post-test. Then, the researcher encoded, analyzed, and interpreted the gathered data using the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS).

The researcher utilized the following statistical tools, mean and standard deviation for descriptive data analysis and paired-sample t - test for inferential data analysis:

Mean. It determined the average score of students' mathematics performance and problem-solving skills.

Standard Deviation. It determined the homogeneity and heterogeneity in the students' mathematics performance and problem-solving skills.

Paired-sample t-test. It ascertained the significant difference in the students' mathematics performance and problem-solving skills before and after they were exposed to instruction using contextualized culture-based teaching and learning lessons.

Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. It ascertained the significant relationships existing between students' mathematics performance and problem-solving skills after the intervention.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Students' Mathematics Performance and Problem-Solving Skills Before and After their Exposure to Contextualized Culture-Based Teaching and Learning Instruction.

Table 1 below shows the result on students' mathematics performance and problem-solving skills before and after their exposure to contextualized culture-based teaching and learning instruction.

The results revealed that students' mathematics performance is "satisfactory" (M=12.34, SD=2.72) before and improved to "very satisfactory" (M=23.71, SD=3.06) after their exposure to contextualized culture-based teaching and learning instruction.

In addition, the result also showed that students' "did not meet expectation" (M=1.03, SD=2.96) in the problem-solving skills before and greatly improved to "outstanding" (M=42.40, SD=8.61) after their exposure to contextualized culture-based teaching and learning instruction.

This means that students' scores in mathematics performance and problem-solving skills improved, is higher, and less scattered if students were exposed to contextualized culture-based instruction.

Students' difficulties were found in the following learning competencies based on the Grade 9 K – 12 curriculum guide before they were exposed to contextualized culture-based instructions: 1) M9AL-lf-2: Solve quadratic inequalities ($M=0.21, SD=0.59$), 2) M9AL-le-1: Solves problems involving quadratic equation and rational algebraic equation ($M=0.82, SD=2.37$), and 3) M9AL-lc-d-1: Solve equations transformable to quadratic equations ($M=1.42, SD=4.83$).

Students' most learned competencies based on the Grade 9 K – 12 curriculum guide after they were exposed to contextualized culture-based instructions: 1) M9AL-lf-2: Solve quadratic inequalities ($M=33.92, SD=6.89$), 2) M9AL-lc-1: Characterize the roots of a quadratic equation using the discriminant ($M=28.32, SD=1.05$), 3) M9AL-la-b-1: Solve Quadratic Equation by Factoring ($M=28.32, SD=1.25$).

It can be observed that the least learned competency before and the most learned competency after students were exposed to contextualize culture-based instruction was the same. This simply implies that the intervention was very effective and greatly improved the said learning competency.

According to the National Council for Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM, 2000), the mastery of the mathematical concepts and problem-solving skills are two very important skills to acquire in modern mathematics which is different from those days.

Table 1							
<i>Least Learned Competencies in Quadratic Equation</i>							
CODE	Learning Competencies	BEFORE		Discriptive Rating	AFTER		Discriptive Rating
		Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
Mathematics Performance		12.32	2.72	Satisfactory	23.71	3.06	Very Satisfactory
M9AL-Ia-1	Illustrate quadratic equation.	21.03	1.32		27.86	1.23	
M9AL-Ia-b-1	Solve quadratic equation by extracting square roots.	16.32	2.06		27.63	1.24	
M9AL-Ia-b-1	Solve Quadratic Equation by Factoring	15.32	1.62		28.32	1.25	
M9AL-Ia-b-1	Solve Quadratic Equation by Completing the Square	5.23	4.52		26.31	4.52	
M9AL-Ia-b-1	Solve Quadratic Equation by Quadratic Formula	7.45	3.53		26.85	3.05	
M9AL-Ic-1	Characterize the roots of a quadratic equation using the discriminant.	23.21	1.26		28.32	1.05	
M9AL-Ic-2	Describe the relationship between the coefficients and the roots of a quadratic equation.	18.29	1.23		24.36	1.56	
M9AL-Ic-d-1	Solve equations transformable to quadratic equations. (Solving Quadratic Equations that are Not Written in Standard Form).	2.63	4.15		14.23	6.25	
M9AL-Ic-d-1	Solve equations transformable to quadratic equations.(Solving Rational Algebraic Equations Transformable to Quadratic Equations)	1.42	4.83		9.52	7.35	
Problem Solving Skills		1.03	2.96	Did not Meet Expectation	42.4	8.61	Outstanding
M9AL-Ie-1	Solve problems involving quadratic equations.	0.82	2.37		33.92	6.89	
M9AL-If-2	Solve quadratic inequalities	0.21	0.59		8.48	1.72	
LEGEND:		Mathematics Performance , 0 – 6 (Did not meet expectations), 6.01 – 12.00 (Fairly Satisfactory), 12.01 – 18.00 (Satisfactory), 18.01- 24.00 (Very Satisfactory), 24.01-30.00 (Outstanding). Problem Solving Skills , 0 – 10 (Did not meet expectations), 10.01 – 20.00 (Fairly Satisfactory), 20.01 – 30.00 (Satisfactory), 30.01- 40.00 (Very Satisfactory), 40.01- 50.00 (Outstanding).					

Difference in the Students' Mathematics Performance before and after their Exposure to Contextualized Culture-Based Instruction

Table 3a shows the difference in the students' mathematics performance before and after their exposure to contextualized culture-based instruction.

The result revealed that there is a significant difference in the students' mathematics performance before and after their exposure to contextualized culture-based instruction $t(34) = -22.418, p = 0.000$. In favor of students' mathematics performance after their exposure to contextualized culture based.

Consequently, students performed better in Mathematics after they were exposed to contextualize culture-based instruction which simply means that this teaching strategy is effective to enhanced students' mathematics performance.

Perin (2011), in a study on facilitating student learning through contextualization, also found out that practitioners who use contextualization observe positive results and the available quantitative evidence indicates that it has the potential to increase students' achievement.

Table 3a

Difference in the Students' Mathematics Performance before and after their Exposure to Contextualized Culture-Based Instruction

	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Std.Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
BEFORE	-22.418*	34	0.000	0.5072	-12.40	-10.34
AFTER						

Note: * $p < 0.05$

Difference in the Students' Problem-Solving Skills before and after their Exposure to Contextualized Culture-Based Instruction

Table 3b shows the difference in the students' problem-solving Skills before and after their exposure to contextualized culture- based instruction.

The result revealed that there is a significant difference in the students' problem-solving skills before and after their exposure to contextualized culture-based instruction $t(34) = -29.927, p = 0.000$. In favor of students' problem-solving skills after their exposure to contextualized culture based.

Hence, students greatly developed their problem-solving skills after they were exposed to contextualized culture-based instruction which simply means that this teaching strategy is also effective to upgrade students' problem-solving skills.

The result of this study was confirmed by Lomibao (2014) who postulated that contextualized problem is effective in improving and enhancing students' problem-solving achievement and conceptual understanding in terms of interpreting, applying, and explaining algebra concepts.

Table 3b

Difference in the Students' Problem-Solving Skills before and after their Exposure to Contextualized Culture-Based Instruction

	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
BEFORE	-29.927*	34	0.000	1.3824	-44.1808	-38.5620
AFTER						

Note: * $p < 0.05$

Correlation between Students' Mathematics Performance and Problem-Solving Skills after their Exposure to Contextualized Culture-Based Instruction

Table 4 shows the correlation between students' mathematics performance and problem-solving skills after their exposure to contextualized culture-based instruction.

Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient result revealed that there is a significant relationship between students' mathematics performance and problem-solving skills $r = 0.583$, $p = 0.000$. This simply means that students' mathematics performance can be explained or predicted by the problem-solving skill after they were exposed to contextualized culture-based instruction. Students who performed well in Mathematics are expected also to perform well in problem solving.

Good conceptual understanding could solve mathematics problems related to real life and could make decision critically. Further, excellent students have high levels of willingness to solve mathematical problems compared to weak or average students (Saritas, 2009).

Table 4

Correlation between Students' Mathematics Performance and Problem-Solving Skills after their Exposure to Contextualized Culture-Based Instruction

	Mathematics Performance	
	r	Sig.(2-tailed)
Problem Solving Skills	*0.583	0.000

Note: $p < 0.01$

Conclusions

This action research found that using contextualized culture-based instruction improved students' mathematics performance and students' problem-solving skills. The following conclusions were drawn from the findings:

1. Teachers introduced and integrated Mathematics concepts in the real-life activities of the students and therefore teachers gained students' interest and pleasure to learn Mathematics applications in their daily life exercises.
2. Students' Mathematics performance and problem-solving skills greatly improved by using contextualized culture-based instruction. This strategy was proven to be effective in making students' learning Mathematics meaningful thus, teachers are encouraged to use and master this teaching strategy in their daily class activities.
3. Used contextualized culture-based instruction was already proven to be effective in enhancing student's Mathematics performance and problem-solving skills. Consequently, the conduct of further research and continuous training for teachers in preparing contextualized culture-based teaching and learning lesson exemplars may help to convince teachers to modify their lesson plans and practice this kind of teaching strategy in their daily classes.

Recommendations

Considering the conclusions drawn and findings of this study, the following recommendations are advanced:

1. Students must be motivated to exert more effort to improve their mathematics performance and use their relevant cultures in developing their problem-solving skills. The teachers must introduce mathematics lessons by integrating relevant culture of the learners.

2. Principals and department heads of mathematics may initiate, support, and provide their teachers with ongoing professional development, led by trainers who have knowledge and expertise on contextualization. Professional development leaders should be experts within the institution rather than outsiders.
3. Policy makers may organize a core group composed of experts to make their own contextualized teaching and learning lesson exemplars in their respective field.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The parent-consent letter was distributed to the participants and will be retrieved before the start of the implementation to make sure that parents are informed about the conduct of the study.

Result of the students' mathematics performance and problem-solving skills will be handled with confidentiality by the researcher. The gathered data were analyzed, interpreted carefully, and honest reporting was ensured by the researcher and not to deceive the public

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